

Promotion, Service Quality, and Personal Selling: Their Effect on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch

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Abstract:- Honda PCX is one of the type of scooter produced by Honda aiming at the premium scooter segment. Nowadays, this type is currently experiencing a surge in purchases at various motorbike distribution companies in Indonesia. This research focused was the automotive industry, motorcycle specifically, which currently obtainable almost all of society levels, genders, and ages. Consumer purchasing decisions are essentially based on various factors, some of which are promotions, service quality, and sales people's personal selling. In recent years, various studies have been carried out to determine the relationship between these variables and obtained mixed results. The promotions, service quality and personal selling have been carried out by the company, both tangibly and intangibly. Turns out, it is not sufficient to provide the sales target's stability of this type up to 60% in the last few months. Therefore, this quantitative research was carried out to find out the influence of promotional variables (X1), service quality (X2), and personal selling (X3) on the purchasing decision a Honda PCX at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. This quantitative research was conducted on 188 consumers with the primary data distributed through questionnaires. The test results using SPSS show that: 1) promotion partially has no effect on consumer purchasing decisions, 2) service quality and personal selling have a partial effect on purchasing decisions, and 3) promotion, service quality, and personal selling have a simultaneous effect on The consumer's decision to buy a Honda PCX at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch is proven by the calculated statistical data.

Keywords:- Promotion; Service Quality ; Personal Selling; Honda, Decision to Buy.

I. INTRODUCTION

Global competition in the automotive industry is a common occurrence. As a pioneer of matik scooters, the Honda PCX, which was released in 2010, has rivals Yamaha NMax, Malaguti Madison 150, and Peugeot Django which are also circulating in the national premium matik market. As reported on the official website of PT Astra Honda Motor as a manufacturer, the Honda PCX is designed to appear more sporty and aggressive to match the style and activities of young people. With a large luggage capacity, Honda PCX also attracts the attention of housewives to support their activities such as shopping. Honda PCX also has a superior power output of 11.8 kW at 8,500 Rpm compared to competitors. The product with the upper middle class matik market segmentation with its advantages designed to be suitable for various circles and metropolitan activities makes the Honda PCX a favorite bike this year.

The growth in sales volume of two-wheeled vehicles of this premium scooter type is motivated by various factors. Appearance, performance, and comfort are considered by customers to choose this type of scooter. This scooter, which can be ridden by all segments, is able to create a comfortable driving impression when traveling long distances due to the ergonomic handlebar position. Therefore, more people are now interested in this latest type of scooter. Automotive businesses are also competing to display this type of vehicle as their sales icon to accelerate the realization of motorcycle sales in their company. [1][2].

The phenomenon that occurred at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch was that the target of Honda PCX motorbikes was not achieved significantly in several months. The target given to PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch every year continues to increase, but the fulfillment of the sales target is still not as stable as expected.

PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch varies greatly in its level of achievement, this is due to several factors such as the level of competition of the same brand with different types. Sales realization also varies due to certain factors such as the scarcity of semiconductor parts. Overall, all standardized sales targets each month are oversold [3]. This is because the company always maintains the quality of service and continues to maintain understanding and the power of personal selling in aggressively informing Honda PCX motorcycle products

Through the explanation above, it can be concluded that Personal Selling is an important process in bridging consumer expectations so that they can be understood by salespeople to then provide a good understanding of the functions and benefits of a product to consumers so that consumers can assess whether the products offered to them are able to provide solutions to needs and in accordance with the budget owned by consumers.

In its product marketing strategy, PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch implements marketing strategies such as promotions, providing excellent service, and personal selling to increase consumer buying interest in products. Personal selling is the spearhead of a company. Through field officers, companies can find out the desires and demands that are currently available to consumers, including consumer demands for products/services marketed by a company. Through this field force, the company also gets orders for the purchase of goods. [4][5].

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that a purchasing decision is based on a need that arises as a problem that consumers want to overcome through the procurement of a good or service. This decision is based on alternative choices which are determined by several factors such as promotion, service quality, personal selling and previous consumer recommendations, both known and unknown. However, previous researchers have had a variety of different results to date. As: 1) [6][7] found that promotion has no effect on purchasing decisions by consumers, 2) [8][16] which states that there is no significant influence between service quality and consumer purchasing decisions, and 3) [9][15] who found that personal selling has no effect on purchasing decisions. Based on these phenomena and theoretical and empirical studies, this study is intended to raise the topic "The Effect of Promotion, Service Quality, and Personal Selling on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT. Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch".

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Promotion

Promotion is an effort made by companies in order to provide or offer products and services with the intention of attracting potential customers to buy or consume the products or services offered by the company. Promotion by [10][11] is defined as a form of direct persuasion through the use of various incentives that can be arranged to stimulate immediate product purchases and / or increase the amount purchased by customers and make consumers satisfied so that they make repeat purchases.

B. Kualitas Pelayanan

[12] said that service quality is the basis for service marketing, because the core of the product being marketed is a quality performance and it is performance that is purchased by customers, therefore the quality of service performance is the basis for service marketing.

C. Personal Selling

Personal Selling is a relationship between two or more people face to face to create a reciprocal relationship in order to create, change, use, and foster communication relationships between producers and consumers. According to (Kotler et al. 2012), personal selling is a form of oral presentation with one or more prospective buyers with the aim of making a purchase.

D. Purchase decision

According to (Kotler and Keller 2016a) suggests that consumer decisions are a stage in the buying process, where consumers will actually buy a product or service. The indicators of purchasing decisions include: 1) Attention (Attention), 2) Interest (Interest), 3) Desire (Desire) and 4) Action (Action)

E. Conceptual framework of research

The conceptual framework of this research can be seen in the following figure:

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

III. RESEACRH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative approach in line with the problems and systematic descriptions presented in the research background. The location of this research was carried out at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch which is located at Jalan Gatot Subroto.KM 8 RT.003/001, Manis Jaya, Curug Subdistrict, Tangerang Regency, Banten. The population in this study were consumers who bought honda PCX motorbikes at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch for the period August 2022 - July 2023 totaling 481 buyers, then the sample was siza using the slovin method and the results of the calculation using the slovin method obtained a sample of 188. Sample withdrawal using non probability sampling technique with accidental sampling. The variables and indicators in this study are presented as follows:

TABLE 1 : RESEARCH VARIABLES AND INDICATORS

No	Variables	Indicator
1	Promotion (X1)	Advertisement
		Sales Promotion
		Public Relations
		Direct Marketing
2	Service Quality (X2)	Reliability
		Responsiveness
		Assurance
		Empathy
		Tangible
3	Personal Selling (X3)	Personal confrontation
		Cultivation
		Response
4	Purchase Decision (Y)	Attention
		Interest
		Desire
		Action

IV. RESULT ANALYSIS

A. Respondent Description

The description of the subject in the following research is carried out in order to find out the characteristics of visitors at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch who are used as subjects in research. The descriptions of respondents in this study are presented as follows:

TABLE 2 : DESCRIPTION OF RESEARCH RESPONDENTS

Description Based on Gender		
Gender	Total	Percentage (%)
Male	112	59,6%
Female	76	40,4%
Total	188	100%
Description by Age		
Age	Total	Percentage (%)
17-27 years old	70	37,0%
28 to 38 years	74	39,0%
39 to 49 years old	39	21,0%
50 years and above	5	3,0%
Total	188	100%
Description Based on Occupation		
Jobs	Total	Percentage (%)
PNS	3	1,6%
TNI/Police	4	2,1%
Private	179	95,2%
Self-employed	0	0%
Housewife	2	1,1%
Total	188	100%

Source: Primary data processed (2023)

Based on the table above, it is known that a total of 112 individuals with a percentage of 59.6% are male and 76 individuals with a percentage of 40.4% are female. This data shows that Honda PCX consumers at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch who are researched are dominated by men. This happens because the Honda PCX is designed with a dashing and sporty design suitable for describing the masculinity of men despite riding a matic scooter type motorbike.

Furthermore, in terms of the age of the respondents, 70 respondents with a percentage of 37.0% were in the range after 17-27 years, 74 respondents with a percentage of 39.0% were 28-38 years old, 39 people with a percentage of 21% were 39-49 years old, and the remaining 3.0% of respondents were 5 people with an age of more than 50 years. The conclusion obtained from this data is that most Honda PCX consumers at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch are those in the age range of 28 years to 38 years.

When viewed in terms of respondents' occupations, the results obtained, a total of 3 people with a percentage of 1.6% work as civil servants, 4 people with a percentage of 2.1% are military / police, 179 people with a percentage of 95.2% are private employees, and the remaining 2 respondents with a percentage of 1.1% are housewives.

B. Research Instrument Testing

➤ Validity Test

Validity testing is used to measure whether the information obtained after the review is valid or not. The results of testing the validity of this study indicate that the value of $r_{Count} > r_{Table}$ and a significant value < 0.05 , so all statement items are declared valid.

➤ Reliability Test

TABLE 3: RESEARCH RELIABILITY TEST

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Value	Description
Promotion (X1)	0,972	Reliable
Service Quality (X2)	0,779	Reliable
Personal Selling (X3)	0,983	Reliable
Purchasing Decision (Y)	0,983	Reliable

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the reliability test table above, it was found that all independent variables: promotion (X2), service quality (X2), personal selling (X3), and the dependent variable: purchasing decisions (Y) have a Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.6 so that all variables used in this study are reliable.

C. Multiple Linear Regression Testing

Multiple linear analysis is used to test the impact of several independent variables on one dependent variable. This analysis is also conducted to determine the direction and magnitude of the impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. The results of the multiple linear regression output in this study are presented in the table below:

TABLE 4: MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.946	.616		1.538	.126
Promotion	-.004	.021	-.010	-.199	.843
Service Quality	.281	.048	.641	5.813	.000
Personal selling	.190	.067	.314	2.848	.005

a. Dependent Variable: Purchasing Decision
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Source: SPSS Analysis Data, processed, 2023

Based on the results of multiple linear regression analysis in the table above, the following regression equation results can be made:

$$Y = 0.946 + 0.004 X_1 + 0.281 X_2 + 0.190 X_3 + 0.117$$

Meaning:

- The constant value is 0.946, which means that if all X variables are 0, the Y value is still 0.946.
- Promotion coefficient (X1): the promotion coefficient value is 0.004. This value implies that every 1 score increase in the quality of promotion is followed by an increase in consumer purchasing decisions worth 0.004 assuming the quality of service (X2) and personal selling (Y3) is fixed.
- Service quality coefficient (X2): The service quality coefficient value is 0.281. This value implies that every time there is an increase of 1 score on service quality, there is also an increase in consumer purchasing decisions worth 0.281, assuming that promotion (X1) and personal selling (Y3) remain.
- The coefficient of personal selling (X3), the promotion coefficient value is 0.190. This value implies that every time there is an increase of 1 score on promotion, there is also an increase in consumer purchasing decisions worth 0.190 with a record of promotion (X1) and service quality (X2) fixed.

V. DISCUSSION

➤ **The Effect of Promotion on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch.** The results in this study contradict most of the previous studies because they are in line with the theory that consumer purchasing decisions are not affected by promotions. It is known that the promotion variable (X1) has a calculated t value of $0.199 < t \text{ table } 1.973$ and a significance of $0.843 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that the promotion variable (X1) partially has no significant effect on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The frequency distribution results show that the highest indicator with an average value of 3.63 is sales promotion, especially in statement item X1.8 where consumers agree that they get a discount when purchasing a Honda PCX on credit. Meanwhile, other indicators, namely public relations and advertising with the same average value of 3.42, were responded neutrally by 188 research respondents. Furthermore, the direct marketing indicator with an average value of 3.34 is the smallest predictor in the relationship between promotion and the decision to buy a Honda PCX at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. At the time of the research, the Honda PCX was a product that was in demand in the market. The high number of interest and the scarcity of semi-conductor parts caused the product to be indented for 1 month. This condition causes the company to be unable to provide promotions in the form of discounts to consumers. The frequency and intensity of promotions are also calculated on the basis of the efficiency and cost effectiveness that must be incurred by the company. The

results of the study which show that there is no influence between promotion and consumer decisions to buy Honda PCX at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch are in line with previous research by (Rahman & Sugianto, 2019) which states that promotion has no significant effect on purchasing decisions and is not in line with previous research (Ardiansyah & Soliha, 2022; AZ, 2018; Restiani Widjaja & Wildan, 2023; Santoso et al., 2022) which states that promotion has an influence on purchasing decisions.

- **The Effect of Service Quality on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch.** The results of this study indicate that the service quality variable (X2) has a t value of $5.813 > t \text{ Table } 1.973$ and a significance of $0.00 < 0.05$. This value indicates that partially there is a significant effect of the service quality variable (X2) on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The frequency distribution results show that the highest indicator with an average value of 3.70 is empathy, especially in statement item X2.10 where the majority of consumers agree that the cashless payment service provided by the company is a form of empathy for consumers to minimize the risk of losing money and facilitate transactions. Meanwhile, other indicators, namely assurance and tangible with the same average value of 3.70, were responded neutrally by 188 research respondents. Furthermore, the responsiveness indicator with an average value of 3.49 is the smallest predictor in the relationship between service quality and the decision to buy a Honda PCX at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. Quality basically covers all customer interactions with the product, from pre-purchase to post-purchase stages. The quality of service from the company is a key element that has an overall impact on purchasing decisions. In modern connected and transparent businesses, companies need to understand that service quality is not just about transactions, but also about building sustainable relationships with consumers. This study proves that service quality has a partial effect on purchasing decisions by Honda PCX consumers at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. This outcome is in line with the study (Ardiansyah & Soliha, 2022; Marlina, 2018; Damanik, 2022) which states that partially service quality has a significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions. However, this result rejects the results of the study by (Marpaung & Mekaniwati, 2020; Restiani Widjaja & Wildan, 2023) which states that there is no significant influence between service quality and consumer purchasing decisions.
- **The Effect of Personal Selling on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch.** The results of this study indicate that the personal selling variable (X3) has a calculated t value of $2.848 > t \text{ table } 1.973$ and a significance of $0.005 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a significant partial influence between the personal selling variable (X3) on the purchasing decision variable (Y). The frequency distribution results show that overall the personal selling variable (X3) is responded with agreement by consumers. Through indicators with the highest mean

value of 3.72 by personal confrontation, followed by response and cultivation indicators of 3.68 and 3.49. The highest predictor with a mean value of 3.73 was obtained from the statements that "Sales Force (Service officers) provide direct service when consumers come to the dealer (X3.1)" and "Sales Force conducts follow-up directly through messages (X3.3). Basically, the ability of personal selling or personal selling involves direct interaction between the salesperson (sales force) and prospective buyers. This activity allows the building of a personal relationship between the salesperson and the customer. A good relationship can increase trust, and this trust can influence purchasing decisions. Through this activity, it can also provide in-depth information, and provide solutions that meet specific customer needs. Personal selling has a significant impact on purchasing decisions because it creates interpersonal interactions that can influence customer perceptions and trust. Therefore, the results of this study are in line with and support previous research by (Cendriyansyah & Mustikasari, 2017; Damayanto & Andriani, 2018; Ghifary Hermansyah, 2022; Nurjaya et al., 2022; Santoso et al., 2022).

- **The Effect of Promotion, Service Quality, and Personal Selling on the Decision to Purchase a Honda PCX Motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch.** This study was conducted with the aim of identifying that there is a simultaneous influence between the independent variables (promotion, service quality, and personal selling) on the dependent variable (purchasing decision) Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. Based on the results of the F test, it is known that the significance value for the influence of the promotion variable (X1), service quality (X2), and personal selling (X3) on the purchasing decision variable (Y) is $F_{\text{Count}} 471.090 > F_{\text{Table}} 2.65$ and significance $0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that all X variables (promotion, service quality, and personal selling) simultaneously or jointly influence the dependent variable purchasing decisions (Y). The highest influence on the promotion variable (X1) on the purchasing decision variable (Y) with an average value of 3.63 through the sales promotion indicator. The highest influence on the service quality variable (X2) on the purchasing decision variable (Y) with an average value of 3.75 through the empathy indicator. The highest influence on the personal selling variable (X3) on the purchasing decision variable (Y) with an average value of 3.72 through the personal confrontation indicator. The results of the research through the F test show that the three X variables simultaneously influence the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. These positive results are in line with previous research (Bramantia, 2016) where promotional variables, service quality, and personal selling are proven to have a simultaneous effect on purchasing decisions for Oriflame products.
- **Promotion is the Dominant Variable on Purchasing Decisions for Honda PCX Motorbikes at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch.** The results of this study identify that the variable that has a dominant

influence on the decision to purchase a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake branch is the Service Quality variable (X2) with a calculated t value of $5.813 > t_{\text{Table}} 1.973$ and a significance of $0.00 < 0.05$. Compared to the personal selling variable (X3) has a calculated t value of $2.848 > t_{\text{Table}} 1.973$ and a significance of $0.005 < 0.05$ and the promotion variable (X1) has a calculated t value of $0.199 < t_{\text{Table}} 1.973$ and a significance of $0.843 > 0.05$ which is proven to have no effect on purchasing decisions (Y). From the results of this study, the 5th hypothesis which states that "It is suspected that promotion has a dominant effect on purchasing decisions through Honda PCX motorbikes at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch" is rejected because it is not statistically proven. These results are not in line with Tahir's research (2018) where it was found that the promotion variable has a dominant influence on consumer purchasing decisions. Service quality can influence purchasing decisions because it presents customer experience in interacting with service providers. This can have an impact on the significance of their perceptions of the product or service offered. Service quality not only affects customer satisfaction but also shapes customer perceptions of the brand or company, which in turn can have a direct impact on their purchasing decisions.

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

Based on the discussion of problem formulation, research objectives, hypotheses, and discussion in the previous chapter, the conclusions that can be presented in this study are as follows:

- Promotion partially has no effect on the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. This indicates that changes that occur in company promotions do not have an implication effect on consumer decisions to buy motorbikes. This can happen because promotion is only one of the predictors of consumer purchasing decisions. The image of PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch with the third highest sales in Indonesia and the image of the quality of Honda PCX products that are known to be superior to other competitors make promotional indicators not the main factor in influencing their purchasing decisions.
- Service quality partially affects the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. This indicates that changes that occur in service quality will have an influence on consumer decisions to buy motorbikes. This can happen because service is a form of company appreciation for buyers or potential buyers. The quality of the service itself will leave a good or bad consumer experience. PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo's services are both physical and non-physical, the company's responsiveness to complaints, to the company's ability to bridge consumer expectations.
- Personal selling partially affects the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. This indicates that changes in the personal selling of a salesperson will affect consumers' decisions to buy products. As consumers agree that the quality of

service of PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch can influence their purchasing decisions, so does the quality of personal selling of its salespeople. The company motto BeST (Give the Best Service) is believed to be a guideline for salespeople to develop their personal selling skills through communicative and informative services.

- Promotion, service quality, and personal selling simultaneously influence the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. Together the variables of promotion, service quality, and personal selling have an effect because today consumers are more critical, selective, and sensitive in making purchases. Consumers will consider more promotions that they feel can provide benefits, on the other hand they also consider how the service they will get both from salespeople and from other company elements. This marketing and service strategy is carried out by PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch to retain customers and attract potential customers to make purchases and provide positive feedback about the company.
- Service quality has a dominant effect on the decision to buy a Honda PCX motorcycle at PT Wahanaartha Ritelindo Jatake Branch. Service quality is a major element in building and maintaining positive relationships between companies and consumers. Consumers will tend to choose companies that can provide satisfying and reliable experiences in their services. This service quality is what will maintain the existence of a consumer.

B. Suggestion

The company should continue to maintain existing promotions and continue to run good relationships with customers and continue to provide updated information about the company such as: free service, discount months, new products or exhibitions and others. Promotions should be carried out both online and offline to continue to be a consistent dissemination of positive information. Online dissemination can be done with social media or websites [13][14][5].

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